

IN VITRO AND IN VIVO ASSESSMENT OF POTENTIAL ANTIMALARIAL ACTIVITY OF EXTRACTS AND SOLVENT FRACTIONS FROM *TRICLISIA GILETTII* (DE WILD) STANER ROOT BARK (MENISPERMACEAEA)

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ABSTRACT

The present study was initiated to evaluate the antimalarial or antiplasmodial activity of aqueous, methanol 80% and total alkaloids extracts as well as solvent fraction from the partition of aqueous extract against *Plasmodium falciparum* NF54 sensible to chloroquine and *Plasmodium falciparum* K1 resistant to chloroquine and pyrimethamine *in vitro* test and towards *Plasmodium yoeli* 67 and *Plasmodium berghei berghei* Anka *in vivo* test. Results revealed that *in vitro* test, aqueous, methanol 80% and total alkaloids extracts as well as all solvent fractions inhibited the growth of both selected *Plasmodium* strain with inhibitory concentrations 50 (IC₅₀) < 10 µg/mL as pronounced activity and produced selective indices of 2.55±0.05, 2.57±0.03 and 2.16±0.04 against *P. falciparum* NF54 respectively and 2.14±0.03, 1.71±0.06 and 1.63±0.03 towards *P. falciparum* K1. Solvent fractions AE1-1 to 1.4 exhibited antiplasmodial activity against *P. falciparum* NF54 with selective indices between 1.30±0.05 and 1.36±0.05 by inhibiting its growth with IC₅₀ values ranging between 5.86±0.09 to 8.44±0.11 µg/mL while they exerted the same effect against *P. falciparum* K1 with IC₅₀ between 6.04±0.08 and 10.32±0.13 µg/mL while solvent fraction ME-1.1 to 1.4 exerted the same effect against both *Plasmodium* parasites with IC₅₀ value from 2.01±0.04 to 8.34±0.06 µg/mL against *P. falciparum* NF54 with SI of 0.83±0.05 to 1.07±0.07. *In vivo* test, results indicated that aqueous and methanol 80% extract administered at dose oral of 400 mg/kg bw produced percentage chemosuppressions of 77.48±0.02 and 85.14±0.07 against *P. yoeli* and 75.13±0.05 and 82.25±0.07 against *P. b. berghei* while total alkaloids extract exerted the same activity by producing percentage chemosuppression of 90.96±0.06 and 90.44±0.03 towards *P. yoeli* and *P. b. berghei* respectively while solvent fractions produced chemosuppression percentages between. Artesunate and Quinine 2HCl used as reference antimalarial products engendered percentage chemosuppression of 90.96±0.08 and 89.36±0.05 against *P. yoeli* 67 respectively and 90.44±0.04 and 89.15±0.07 towards *P. b. berghei* respectively. Aqueous, methanol and total alkaloids extracts, showed weak activity compared to Quinine and Artesunate against both *plasmodium* strains *P. yoeli* and *P. b. berghei*.

1. INTRODUCTION

The disease malaria considered as a life-threatening infectious disease caused by Plasmodium parasites, may be caused by at least five different species like *P. falciparum* (most severe), *P. vivax* (relapsing), *P. ovale*, *P. malariae*, and *P. knowlesi* (from monkeys) (Patel et al., 2013, Yang et al., 2021, Chani et al., 2022). But, there are approximately 156 named species of *Plasmodium* which infect various species of vertebrates. Four species are considered true parasites of humans, as they utilize humans almost exclusively as a natural intermediate host: *P. falciparum*, *P. vivax*, *P. ovale* and *P. malariae*. However, there are periodic reports of simian malaria parasites being found in humans, most reports implicating *P. knowlesi*. At the time of this writing, it has not been determined if *P. knowlesi* is being naturally transmitted from human to human via the mosquito, without the natural intermediate host (macaque monkeys, genus *Macaca*). Therefore, *P. knowlesi* is still considered a zoonotic malaria. *P. falciparum* was the most dangerous parasite often causes malaria relapse reaching some time to death (Anonyme, 2025).

This disease is the major public health concern worldwide, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions particularly in sub-Saharan Africa where it is considered as one of the most serious health problems. Globally, there were estimated 229 millions cases and 409.000 deaths from malaria in 2019 (WHO, 2020). This situation is due to the great increase in the resistance of malaria parasites to used antiplasmodial drugs and the limited number of effective drugs are the great challenge in the treatment of the disease. Most cases and deaths occurred in the WHO African countries and mainly affect children and pregnant women (OMS, 2017, Wen-Hu et al., 2018).

Malaria generally occurs in areas where environmental conditions allow parasite multiplication in the vector. Malaria today is usually restricted to tropical and subtropical areas and altitudes below 1,500 m., although in the past malaria was endemic in much of North America, Europe and even parts of northern Asia, and today is still present on the Korean peninsula. However, this present distribution could be affected by climatic changes and population movements. *Plasmodium falciparum* is the predominant species in the world. *P. vivax* and *P. ovale* are traditionally thought to occupy complementary niches, with *P. ovale* predominating in Sub-Saharan Africa and *P. vivax* in the other areas; but their geographical ranges do overlap. These two species are not always distinguishable on the basis of morphologic characteristics alone, and the use of molecular tools will help clarify their diagnosis and exact distribution. *P. malariae* has wide global distribution, being found in South America, Asia, and Africa, but it is less frequent than *P. falciparum* in terms of association with cases of infection. *P. knowlesi* is found in southeast Asia (Anonyme, 2025).

The symptoms of uncomplicated malaria can be rather non-specific and the diagnosis can be missed if health providers are not alert to the possibility of this disease. Since untreated malaria can progress to severe forms that may be rapidly (<24 hours) fatal, malaria should always be considered in patients who have a history of exposure (mostly: past travel or residence in disease-endemic areas). The most frequent symptoms include fever and chills, which can be accompanied by headache, myalgias, arthralgias, weakness, vomiting, and diarrhea. Other clinical features include splenomegaly, anemia, thrombocytopenia, hypoglycemia, pulmonary or renal dysfunction, and neurologic changes. The clinical presentation can vary substantially depending on the infecting species, the level of parasitemia, and the immune status of the patient. Infections caused by *P. falciparum* are the most likely to progress to severe, potentially fatal forms with central nervous system involvement (cerebral malaria), acute renal failure, severe anemia, or acute respiratory distress syndrome. Other species can also have severe manifestations. Complications of *P. vivax* malaria include splenomegaly (with, rarely, splenic rupture), and those of *P. malariae* include nephrotic syndrome ((Anonyme, 2025).

Malaria is a severe, potentially fatal disease that requires immediate medical attention. Treatment involves prescription antimalarial medications aimed at killing the parasite, with the specific drugs and duration depending on the parasite species, the severity of the illness, the patient's age, and where the infection was acquired. Malaria is a severe and potentially fatal disease that requires prompt treatment with prescription antimalarial drugs to kill the parasite and prevent life-threatening complications. The specific treatment regimen depends on several factors, including the infecting parasite species, the severity of the illness, the patient's age and health status (e.g., pregnancy), and the geographic area where the infection was acquired due to varying drug resistance patterns. The principal treatment of malaria includes.

- **Prompt Diagnosis and Treatment:** Suspected malaria should be diagnosed with a laboratory test (microscopy or rapid diagnostic test) and treated promptly, ideally within 24 hours of symptoms starting.
- **Species Identification:** Identifying the specific *Plasmodium* species (e.g., *P. falciparum*, *P. vivax*) is crucial as different species respond to different medications and some can cause more severe complications or relapses.
- **Severity Assessment:** Patients are categorized as having either uncomplicated or severe malaria. Severe malaria is a medical emergency requiring hospitalization and aggressive intravenous therapy.
- **Drug Resistance:** Treatment guidelines consider the potential for drug resistance based on the geographic area where the infection was acquired.

Taking accounts of the wide-spread resistance of the parasite *Plasmodium falciparum* against the current antimalarial drugs not easily accessible to people in developing countries, they turn to traditional medicine mainly based on medicinal plant species claimed by traditional healers to be effective against malaria in their daily practice and find some reliefs after a long period treatment (Wilcos and Bodeker, 2004, Kikweta *et al.*, 2023).

Trigisia gilletii, synonyms *Triclisia flava* Excell, *Tiliacora gilletii* De Wil, *Tiliacora gilletii* De Wild. in Bull. Jard. Bot. État Bruxelles 3: 255 (1911), *Triclisia dictyophylla* Diels, *Tiliacora trichantha* Diels in H.G.A.Engler (ed.), Pflanzent., IV, 94: 63 (1910), *Triclisia flava* Exell in J. Bot. 64(Suppl.): 12 (1926) Inst. Roy. Congo Belge 4: 430 (1933), *Triclisia semnophylla* Diels ex Engl. in H.G.A.Engler & O.Drude, Veg. Erde 9(III 1): 178 (1915), common names *Gilletii Triclisia*, *Triclisia Gilletii* and *Gilletii Tree* (selinawamuii.com/plants/menispermaceae/Triclisia-gilletii, 2025).

T. gilletii is a voluble liane, stem can reach 10 cm diameter.; young twigs slightly pubescent, coming glabres, to greyish bark, striated longitudinally. Leaves to robuste petioles, inflated at the base, geniculated and thickened to head, reaching 20 cm long, slightly tomentose, becoming glabrescent, limbs widely rounded, subcutaneous to base, acuminate to head, reaching 32 cm long and 27 cm wide, coriaceous, glabre on 2 faces, nervures secondary nerves 3-5 pairs, whose have 1-2 basilar, the majority jointed between them to coast proximity, creating with tertiary nerves very strong network or mesh on the inferior face of the limb. Inflorescences' ♂ in panicles rarely more than 3 cm long, bulging on adult twigs or to the basis of young twigs sheathed, rachis tomentose, hairy or shaggy pediciled of ± 2 mm long, bracts 2, subcorded-ovales, of ± 0,5 mm long, hairy or shaggy-tomentose. Flowers ♂ with 9 sepals, hairy or shaggy-tomentose: 3 exterior subcorded-ovales, of ± 1 mm long, 3 medians ± similar to exterior, of ± 1 mm long, 3 interior elliptic-ovales, of 4-4,5 mm long and 2-2,5 mm wide, petals 3, rounded, very small, of ± 0,5 mm long, stamens 6, free, of 4-5 mm long, to cylindrical filament, tenuous or slight, of ± 4 mm long, anther ovoides, of ± 1 mm long, box or chest to dehiscence longitudinal. Inflorescences' ♀ similar to inflorescences ♂. flowers' ♀ to bracts and sepals as in flowers ♂; petal absent; carpels 50-60; ovaries tomentose; styles ± cylindrical of ± 1,5 mm long and glabres. Drupe obovoid, compressed, truncated to the basis, caudate-acuminate to head, to acumen curved of ± 2,5 cm long and ± 1,7 cm wide exocarps ± verrucous, mesocarpe subleshy of ± 2 mm thickness in sicco, endocarpe very heavy or rough, dur. Seeds of ± 1-1,5 cm long and 1 cm wide.

Its habitat is Equatorial primitive marshy forest and galleries forestry.

For its uses, the liane *Efiri* has subjected to several studies on biochemical point. In fact it has believed that this liane contained a strong antimalarial substance more effective than quinine. Results from the therapeutic essays with total plant extract at dose 3 to 10 more strong than used with quinine, have permitted to conclude the complete inefficiency or inefficacy of *Efiri*. The indigenous use it as remedy against diarrhoea, pyorrhoea and arrow poison. (<https://tropical.ferns.info/viewtropical.php?id=Triclisia+dictyophylla>, 2025).

The macerated root is taken as an abortifacient and menagogue. A decoction is drunk as a vermifuge, whereas the roots are taken raw to treat venereal diseases. The grated roots are taken to treat snakebites and expel roundworms. The root pulp or root sap is rubbed into scarifications to treat joint pains, epileptic attacks, oedema, venereal diseases and anaemia. A bark or root decoction is used as a wash to calm palpitations. A decoction of the twig bark is widely taken to treat fever and malaria, and also to treat diarrhoea, stomach problems and purulent catarrh. The powdered stem bark is used in the treatment of leprosy. A root bark decoction is taken as a treatment for stomach problems and dysentery, convulsive coughing and feverish stiffness of the limbs.

The leaf juice is used to ease coughs. The leaves are suspended from the ceiling to help children with breathing problems. The juice of young leaves is diluted and administered as a painkiller to patients with mental health problems during attacks. The characteristic bioactive compounds in the plant are bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloids and related dioxin alkaloids (<https://tropical.ferns.info/viewtropical.php?id=Triclisia+dictyophylla>, 2025).

From phytochemical and biological study, a range of alkaloids have been found in the roots, stems and leaves. *Triclisia gilletii* (DeWild.) Staner is a woody climber indigenous to Ghana and other parts of West Africa. Extracts of the plant have been used medicinally and as an arrow poison. Chromatography of an extract of the leaves afforded the new bisbenzylisoquinoline dibenzodioxin alkaloids gillettine and isogillettine-N-oxide as well as two other bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloids, obamegine and stebisimine. A bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloid named 'cycleanine' has been isolated from ethanol extract of *Triclisia subcordata* and shown to potently ($IC_{50} < 2.4 \mu\text{g/mL}$) inhibit tumor cells growth in the ovarian cancer, Ovar-8 and A2780 cell lines, using the Sulforhodamine B assay. The IC_{50} of cycleanine on human normal ovarian surface epithelial cells was $35 \pm 1 \mu\text{M}$, thus suggesting modest selectivity toward cancer cells. A methanol extract of the stem bark has shown strong activity against *Plasmodium falciparum* *in vitro* and significant effect against *Trypanosoma brucei*.

(https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231715200_Constituents_of_West_African_Medicinal_Plants_XXVIII_Additional_Alkaloids_of_Triclisia, 2025). Aqueous methanol, total alkaloids and solvent fractions from the partition of *T. gilettii* root and stem bark collected in Kinshasa were reported to exhibit antiplasmodial activity *in vitro* against isolated *Plasmodium falciparum* sensible to chloroquine infected human blood and against *P. falciparum* K1 strain resistant to chloroquine and pyrimethamine with IC₅₀ values < 10 µg/mL and the cytotoxicity against MRC-5 cell line was also investigated, and all tested samples were devoid with cytotoxic effect towards this cell line (Kikweta *et al.*, 2013).

The present investigation was conducted to evaluate the antimalarial activity of aqueous, methanol 80% and solvent fractions from *Triglisia giletti* root bark against *Plasmodium falciparum* NF54 sensible to chloroquine and *P. falciparum* K1 strain resistant to chloroquine and pyrimethamine and *in vivo* evaluation towards *Plasmodium yoelii* 67 and *P. berghei berghei*.

2. MATERIELS AND METHODS

2.1. Vegetal material

Fresh roots of *Triglisia giletti* were collected in Kinzaweta collectivity in Bas-Congo (Democratic Republic of Congo). The plant was identified at Institut National d'Etudes et de Recherches en Agronomie (INERA), Faculty of Sciences and Technologies, Department of Biology, University of Kinshasa/Kinshasa where a voucher specimen No Tg12480rb was deposited in the herbarium of this institute.

Figure 1: *Triglisia giletti* leaves and twigs.

2.2. Preparation of extracts and fractionation of extracts

50 g of fresh *Triclisia gilettii* root bark were dried at normal temperature for three days, cut in small pieces and reduced to powder using an traditional mortar resulting in a powder kept in a brune bottle for use to avoid contamination. 50 g of root bark powder were mixed with 300 mL distilled water and heated on hot plaque at 100°C for 15 minutes. After cooling and filtration on sterile cotton and paper filter Whatman N° 1, the resulting filtrate was evaporated in rotative

evaporator giving dried extract of 22.13 g denoted as Tgrb-1.

On the other hand, 20 g of plant material was mixed with 200 mL methanol 80% and macerated for 24h. After filtration in the same condition described above, a macerate was obtained. The macerate was exhaustively percolated with the same solvent and filtered in the same conditions as described above. The macerate and percolate were combined and evaporated *in vacuo* giving a dried extract denoted as Tgrs-2 (12.67 g).

Next, an amount of each extract Tgrb-1 and 2 (10 g) was dissolved in 200 mL distilled water and treated as described above. The resulting filtrate was exhaustively and successively extracted with solvents of different polarities like chloroform, ethylacetate and *n*-butanol. All fractions including residual aqueous fraction was treated as described above giving corresponding dried extracts denoted as Tgrb-1.1 (1.25 g), Tgrb-1.2 (2.65 g), Tgrb-1.3 (1.52 g) and Tgrb-1.4 (3.25 g) and Tgrb-2.1 (1.54g) Tgrb-2.2 (2.71 g), Tgrb-2.3 (1.72 g) and Tgrb-2.4 (3.45 g) for chloroform, ethylacetate, *n*-butanol and residual aqueous fractions from aqueous extract Tgrb-1 and methanol 80% extract respectively (Tgrb: *Triclisia gilettii* root bark).

2.3. Chemical screening

The confirmatory qualitative phytochemical screening of plant extracts was performed to identify the main classes of compounds (tannins, saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids, phenols, glycosides, steroids, and terpenoids) present in the extracts following standard protocols.^[26-28]

Test for Tannins

About 2 mg of the plant extract was dissolved in 5 mL distilled water and 1 mL Stiasny reagent (formol + HCl conc. was added to the mixture giving a brune precipitate for catechin tannins as positive test. The mixture was filtered on paper filter Whatman n° 1 and in the filtrate, 1 mL FeCl₃ 5% WAS added giving grey coloration for gallic tannins as positive test.

Test for Alkaloids

The plant extract was dissolved in 5 mL of water, filtered, and Then, 1 mL of the heated mixture was combined with 1 mL of Mayer-Wagner reagent or Dragendorff reagents giving white yellowish and orange precipitate respectively as positive tests.

Test for Saponins

About 0.5 milliliters of the extract and 5 mL of distilled water were combined and agitated. Then, the formation of foam persisting during 10 minutes confirmed the presence of saponins.

Test for Flavonoids and Glycosides

200 mg of the plant extract was mixed with 10 mL of ethanol and filtrated. Two mL of the filtrate, concentrated HCl, and magnesium ribbon (Shinoda

reagent) were mixed. The formation of a pink or red color indicates the presence of flavonoids. Adding 1 mL of distilled water and NaOH to 0.5 mL of crude extract, the formation of a yellowish color indicated the presence of glycosides.

Test for Steroids

About 1 mL of the crude extract was combined with 10 mL of chloroform and 10 mL of sulfuric acid, and the formation of the bilayer (red top layer and greenish bottom layer) reveals the presence of steroids.

Test for Terpenoids

The presence of terpenoids was determined by the formation of a reddish-brown color in the test for terpenoids, which included mixing of 0.5 mL of crude extract with 2 mL of chloroform and 3 mL of sulfuric acid.

Test for Phenols

About 1 mL of the extract was combined with three drops of FeCl₃, and 1 mL of K₂Fe (CN)₆ (Barton reagent). The formation of brown precipitate and blue color respectively confirmed the presence of phenols.

Test for polysaccharides

To 1 mL solution of extract, formol + H₂SO₄ conc; was added giving various coloration as positive test.

Reductor sugars

To 1 mL solution of extract, 1M Fehling reagent was added, mixed and boiled giving a red color as positive test.

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) Test

Thin layer chromatography was performed on TLC plate (silica gel pre-coated with layer thickness of 0.2 mm, Merck, Germany) to confirm the presence of some phytochemicals using hexane/ethyl acetate 8:2 as mobile phase for steroids and terpenoids, BAW 4:1:5 (top layer) for flavonoids, CHCl₃/MeOH/NH₃ 10: 9:1:1 for alkaloids. Spots were applied using capillary tube 1.5 cm from the bottom marked by a line ruled using a pin. The sample spotted on the plate was allowed to dry before the plate was placed into the chromatographic tank which was covered immediately. When the solvent reaches the top of the plate, the plate was removed, marked and dried. The number of the spots was detected under UV at 254 and 366 nm wavelengths and spraying with appropriate reagent (Harborne, 1998, Trease and Evans, 2000).

3. Evaluation of antiplasmodial activity of extracts and solvent fractions

3.1. Antiplasmodial and cytotoxic activity *in vitro* test

The *in vitro* antiplasmodial activity of aqueous and methanol 80% extracts and their respective solvent fractions against *Plasmodium falciparum* NF54 and *P. falciparum* K1 sensitive and resistant to chloroquine respectively from the laboratory of Parasitology of Prof Cos, university of Antwerp, Belgium, was carried out by

using the method previously described by Kuypers *et al.* (2006) and Mesia *et al.* (2008)

3.2. Antiplasmodial evaluation *in vivo* test

The *in vivo* antiplasmodial activity of aqueous and methanol 80% of *T. gillettii* rook bark was evaluated in the 4-day suppressive test against *Plasmodium yoelii* 67 and *P. b. berghei* Anka infected mice using the method previously described by Peeters and Robinson, 1992, with some modifications (Tona *et al.*, 2001). These strains were obtained from the laboratory of parasitology in University of Antwerp, Belgium. White Swiss (OF1) mice weighing 23.2±1.7 g were divided in following groups with 5 mice each.

- Group I received orally 5 ml saline solution (0.9% NaCl)/kg bodyweight (bw) as negative control,
- Group II received in the same way quinine 10 mg/kg bw as positive control,
- Groups III and IV were orally administered 200 (a) and 400 (b) mg of each extract dissolved in distilled water.

All selected rats were intraperitoneally injected with 1 x 10⁷ of parasitized erythrocytes with each selective *Plasmodium*. The test mice were immediately treated daily from day 1 to 3 with respective of each extract. Each day from day-1 to 4? A film was prepared from tail-blood sample from each mice and stained with Giemsa so that the level of parasitaemia expressed in percentage could be recorded as half the number of schizonts with at least three nuclei each, counted in 200 erythrocytes. On day 4, the mean parasitaemia in each mice was determined in order to calculate the percentage chemosuppression as A-B/A x 100 where A was the mean parasitaemia in negative control and B the mean parasitaemia in tested groups.

3.3. Cytotoxicity evaluation

The cytotoxicity of extracts, fractions and isolated compounds was evaluated on MRC-5 cells (human lung fibroblasts) cultured in MEM medium, supplemented with 20 mM L-glutamine, 16.5 mM NaHCO₃, 5% foetal calf serum and 2% P/S (penicillin/streptomycin) solution according to the MTT procedure as previously described (Cos *et al.*, 2006; Mesia *et al.*, 2008; Tuenter *et al.*, 2016). The 50% cytotoxic concentration (CC₅₀) for each sample was derived from the dose response curves. A selectivity index (SI), corresponding to the ratio between cytotoxic and antiparasitic concentrations, was calculated as SI = CC₅₀ / IC₅₀ (Kuypers *et al.*, 2006). If SI < 1: test sample was considered as cytotoxic while SI > 1 in the test sample was considered as non cytotoxic (Camacho *et al.*, 2003).

3.4. Evaluation of acute and subacute toxicity of aqueous extract

Mice were randomly and divided in 5 groups of 5 mice each.

- Group I received orally 5 mL distilled water as negative group,

-Group II with mice received once 5000 mg/kg bw of aqueous extract in acute toxicity
 -Groups III to V were orally administered separately 500, 1000 and 5000 mg/kg bw of aqueous extract.

The acute toxicity test was performed according the experimental method Guideline 423 of the Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) with an initial and only dose of 5000 mg/kg bw while the subacute toxicity was carried out by the oral administration separately oral doses of 500, 1000 and 5000 mg/kg bw to selected mice. After administration, each mice was kept in an individual plastic cage and following parameters were observed during 28 days of the test: irritability, touch response, tail grip response, contortion, posterior train position, straightening reflex, body tone ataxia, mobility, tremors, convulsion, death, etc. They were weighted daily.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Chemical screening

The root bark of *Trichilia gillettii* (*T. gillettii* was the correct taxonomic name, likely what was intended by the

user's query *Triglisia gilletii*) contains several chemical compounds, primarily belonging to the class of limonoids such as deacetylkhivorin and 3,7-dide acetyl-6 α -hydroxykhivorin belonging to the class of limonoids.

Major phytochemical identified in *Triglisia gillettii* root bark in the present study were presented in Table 1 below. Results revealed *T. gillettii* root bark contained alkaloids, flavonoids, coumarines, polyphenols, polysaccharides, reductor sugars, saponines, steroids, terpenoides, tannins (gallic and cathechic). Consenquently, anthocyanes, anthraquinones and cardiotoxic heterosides were not identified in *T. gillettii* root bark collected in Kinzaweta collectivity in Bas-Congo (Democratic Republic of Congo). It was very difficult to compare ours results to other previously published which were not found in the literature.

Table 1: Major phytochemical identified.

Groups	Results	Groups	Results
Alkaloids	+++	Polysaccharides	+++
Anthraquinones	-	Proanthocyanidins	++
Anthocyanes	=	Reductor sugars	+++
Cardiotoxic heterosides	-	Saponins	++
Coumarins	++	Steroids	++
Flavonoids	++	Terpenoids	++
Glycosides	++	Tannins (cathechic and gallic)	++
Polyphenols	+++		

Thus, it was considered the present study as the first report for the first time the chemical composition of *T. gillettii* root bark.

3.2 Antiplasmodial activity

For good interpretation and understanding of the activity developed by test samples in the present study, following criteria were adopted: $IC_{50} \leq 10$ $\mu\text{g/mL}$: pronounced activity, $10 < IC_{50} \leq 20$ $\mu\text{g/mL}$: good activity, $20 < IC_{50} \leq 30$ $\mu\text{g/mL}$: moderate activity, $30 < IC_{50} \leq 50$ $\mu\text{g/mL}$: weak activity, $IC_{50} > 50$ $\mu\text{g/mL}$: inactive.

3.2.1. Effects of extracts and solvent fractions *in vitro* test against selected *Plasmodium* strains

Results revealed that, tested against *Plasmodium falciparum* NF54 sensible to chloroquine, the majority of tested samples inhibited the growth of this *Plasmodium* strain with inhibitory concentrations 50 (IC_{50}) less than 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ as pronounced activity. The most active sample was methanol EM-2 extract exhibited this activity with IC_{50} of 2.07 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ followed by aqueous EA-1 extract showing IC_{50} value of 2.54 \pm 0.06 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and the less active sample was chloroform AE-1.1 solvent fraction (IC_{50} = 9.26 \pm 0.09 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). All solvent fractions from the partition of aqueous EA-1 extract EA-

1.1 to 1.4 with IC_{50} values between 5.75 \pm 0.05 and 10.26 \pm 0.09 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ as pronounced and good activity respectively according the case, exhibited low activity compared to EM-1.1 to 2.4 solvent fractions from the partition of methanol ME-1 exerting pronounced activity by producing IC_{50} values ranging between 4.14 \pm 0.05 and 6.23 \pm 0.05 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

When tested against *P. falciparum* K1 strain resistant for chloroquine and pyrimthamine, all test samples displayed inhibition growth of this *Plasmodium* strain with IC_{50} value < 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ as pronounced activity. Methanol ME-1 extract showed high activity with IC_{50} value compared to aqueous extract EA-1 (IC_{50} = 2.54 \pm 0.04 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with the less active sample as chloroform AE-1.1 from the partition of aqueous extract AE-1. As perceived the level of antiplasmodial activity toward *P. falciparum* NF54, all solvent fractions ME-1 to 1.4 with IC_{50} between 6.12 \pm 0.07 and 9.67 \pm 0.03 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ as pronounced activity from the partition of methanol ME--1 extract displayed high activity compared to those from the partition of aqueous extract presenting IC_{50} values ranging from 6.04 \pm 0.08 and 12.34 \pm 0.10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ as pronounced and good activity respectively according the case. All extracts produced selective index (SI) with values > 1

expressing their selective antimalarial activity against both *Plasmodium strains* (Camacho *et al.*, 2003).

Moreover, the majority of solvent fractions AE-11 to 1.4 and ME-1.1 to 1.4 from the partition of aqueous extract

AE-1 and methanol 80% ME-1 extract respectively, showed also good selective index with values > 1 expressing their selective antimalarial activity.

Table 1: Antiplasmodial activity of extracts and solvent fractions against *Plasmodium* strain and cytotoxic activity *in vitro*.

Sample codes	MRC-5 (CC ₅₀ , µg/ml)	PFNF54, IC ₅₀ , µg/mL	PFK-1, IC ₅₀ , µg/ml	SI/PNF54	SIPFK-1
AQUEOUS EXTRACT					
AE-1	5.45±0.04	2.13±0.06	2.54±0.04	2.55±0.05	2.14±0.03
AE-1.1	7.63±0.06	5.86±0.09	8.23.34±0.10	1.30±0.05	0.92±0.06
AE-1.2	6.45±0.03	5.75±0.05	6.04±0.08	1.21±0.06	1.06±0.08
AE-1.3	8.63±0.11	8.54±0.11	10.32±0.13	1.01±0.07	0.83±0.05
AE-1.4	9.72±0.13	7.11±0.04	9.05±0.08	1.36±0.05	1.07±0.05
METHANOL EXTRACT					
EM-1	5.32±0.02	2.07±0.04	3.11±0.06	2.57±0.03	1.71±0.06
EM-1.1	7.32±0.07	8.34±0.06	10.11±0.07	0.88±0.06	0.72±0.08
EM-1.2	6.30±0.05	4.14±0.05	6.12±0.07	1.52±0.10	1.03±0.08
EM-1.3	8.26±0.08	7.55±0.04	9.67±0.03	1.10±0.05	0.85±0.04
EM-1.4	9.41±0.11	6.23±0.05	8.42±0.05	1.51±0.12	1.11±0.13
ME-3	3.34±0.05	1.54±0.04	2.05±0.06	2.16±0.04	1.63±0.03
Artesunate	10.43±0.05	1.54±0.03	2.23±0.04	6.77±0.06	4.67±0.04
Quinine 2HCl	15.03±0.06	2.15±0.04	4.13±0.02	7.00±0.04	3.64±0.04

AE: aqueous extract, AE-1-1 to 1.4a and ME-1.1 to 1.4: chloroform, ethylacetate, *n*-butanol and residual aqueous solvent fractions from the partition of aqueous EA-1 extract and methanol 80% EM-1 extract respectively.

But someone such as chloroform AE-1.1 SI = 0.92±0.08 and *n*-butanol AE-1.3 SI = 0.83±0.03 from aqueous extract AE-1, and ME-1.1 from methanol ME-1 extract, SI = 0.72 presented SI < 1 as a sign of their cytotoxic effect on the selected cell line MRC5 and were devoid with selective antimalaric action (Camacho *et al.*, 2003).

In addition, our results compared to those reported previously by Kikweta *et al.* (2013) using *P. falciparum* sensible to chloroquine isolated in infected blood of some patients in hospital, and another *P. falciparum* K-1 strain for aqueous and methanol extract and their respective solvent fractions from root bark of *T. gillettii* collected in Kinshasa, revealed that all samples exhibited high antiplasmodial *in vitro* activity against both selected *P. falciparum* NF54 and K1, and *in vivo* against *P. yolei* 67 and *P. b. berghei* compared to the same samples from *T. gillettii* root bark collected in Kinzaweta collectivity in Bas-Congo in the same country. Thus, this difference of activity may be due to the origin of the used strains *in vitro* and *in vivo* tests and the collection of the plant material.

3.2.2. *In vivo* antiplasmodial activity of aqueous et methanol 80% extracts

Results recorded in antiplasmodial *in vivo* test were presented in Table 2. They revealed that the oral administration of all oral dose in all extracts, caused significant reduction of parasitemia in all treated infected mice in dose dependent manner (Table 2). Administered

at high dose of 400 mg/kg bw, they reduced considerably percentage chemosuppression of parasitemia in infected mice with *P. yolei* by 77.48±0.08% and with *P. b. berghei* by 75.13±0.11% for aqueous extract AE-1. Methanol ME-1 extract reacted in the same manner aqueous extract by producing 78.52±0.06 and 75.54±0.12% chemosuppression towards *P. both Plasmodium yoeli* and *b.berghei* respectively. Total alkaloid ME-3 extract reacted also the same manner as aqueous EA-1 and methanol ME-1 by decreasing parasitemia in treated mice infected with both *Plasmodium* strains in dose dependent manner (Table 2). Given orally at high dose of 400 mg/kg bw, it produced chemosuppression percentage of parasitemia induced by both *Plasmodium* strains to 85.70±0.04% towards *P. yolei* and 84.96±0.10% against *P. b. berghei*. Its antiplasmodial *in vivo* was found to high confronted to that of aqueous AE-1 and methanol ME-1 extract. Our results were only qualitatively in good agreement with Kikweta *et al.*; (2013) who reported previously the antiplasmodial activity *in vivo* of these extracts.

Table 2: Effects of extracts on selected *Plasmodium in vivo* test.

Sample codes	Treatment (mg/kg bw)	%P. in <i>P. yolei</i>	%P. in <i>b. berghei</i>	% Inhibition of <i>P. yolei</i>	% inhibition on <i>P. b. berghei</i>
AE-1	200	8.14±0.05	7.16±0.07	71.05±0.04	75.0.2±0.08
	400	6.33±0.10	7.13±0.04	77.48±0.08	75.13±0.11
ME-1	200	6.04±0.12	7.01±0.08	78.52±0.06	75.54±0.12
	400	4.15±0.08	5.02±0.10	85.24±0.13	82.25±0.08
ME-3	200	4.11±0.07	4.87±0.12	85.38±0.06	83.01±0.08
	400	4.02±0.10	4.31±0.08	85.70±0.04	84.96±0.10
Artesunate	10	2.54±0.06	2.74±0.05	90.96±0.08	90.44±0.03
Quinine 2HCl	10	3.05±0.04	3.11±0.07	89.36±0.05	89.15±0.07

%P. in *P. yolei* 67 and P; in *b. berghei*: percentage of parasitemia in *Plasmodium yolei* and *Plasmodium berghei* *berghei* Anka, AE-1: aqueous extract, ME-1: methanol 80% extract ME-3 : total alkaloids extract.

Only against *P. b. berghei* and for the present this study to our knowledge, it was the first time to report the antiplasmodial activity *in vitro* against *P. falciparum* NF54 of extracts and solvent fractions and *in vivo* against *P. yolei* of extracts of *T. gillettii* root.

Moreover, general mechanisms action of antiplasmodial activity of some secondary metabolites were previously reported indicating that alkaloids acted as antiplasmodial by attacking *Plasmodium* parasite through multiple mechanisms, primarily by inhibiting hemozoin formation (preventing detoxification of heme), disrupting parasite membranes, interfering with DNA and RNA/protein synthesis, modulating parasite signaling pathways and targeting specific enzymes like PfATP4 which messes with ion balance leading to parasite death, often by affecting the digestive vacuole stage of the parasite as seen with the quinolinic alkaloid quinine interfering with heme polymerization and indolic alkaloid cryptolepine targeting multiple pathways offering hope against drug resistant and sensitive malaria by hitting targets distinct from older drugs. Other particular mechanisms included.

- hemozoin inhibition preventing the parasite from detoxifying heme into inert hemozoin crystals leading to toxic buildup and parasite death,
- ionic and osmotic homeostasis disruption that regulated sodium and osmotic balance causing parasite collapse,
- DNA/RNA protein interference can intercalate into or disrupt nucleic acid biosynthesis and protein production, hindering parasite replication,
- Enzyme inhibition that can target vital parasite enzymes such as those in fatty acid
- Synthetic pathway (FAS-II) as seen with Amaryllidaceae alkaloids for example, Garcia-Diaz -synergistic effects that can enhance or increase the activity of existing drugs like chloroquine, offering new combination therapies,
- Targeting multiple pathways in which alkaloids possessed often multiple mode of action (multiple targeted) or slow-acting properties, making them effective towards drug-resistant where single-target drugs fail.

Flavonoids acted as antiplasmodial agents by disrupting the malaria parasite's vital functions, primarily by

inhibiting fatty acid biosynthesis (FAS-II) pathway enzymes like FABg, FABz, FABi crucial for parasite survival, but absent in humans, and by interfering with heme detoxification and targeting multiple *Plasmodium* pathways such as inhibition parasite growth by interfering with crucial enzymes like falcipai-2, plasmepsin, PfDXR, PFLDH, disrupted heme detoxification (β -hematin formation), interfered with the parasite's metabolism/lifecycle, potentially blocked red blood cell invasion and can synergize with existing drugs like artemisinin, making them promising for new antimalarial therapies, especially towards drug-resistant strains. Methoxylated flavonoids bound to heme to prevent the parasite from neutralizing toxic heme products and also by affecting parasite nutrient uptake with some showed synergistic effects with existing drugs like artemisinin.

Particular mechanisms included

- Enzyme inhibition by which flavonoids bound to and inhibited essential parasite enzymes including proteases, metabolic enzymes PfDXR (deoxy-D-xylose-5 phosphate reductoisomerase) and pFLDH (lactose dehydrogenase),
- Heme detoxification inhibition where these compounds blocked the formation of hemozoin (β -hematin), as a toxic byproduct of heme digestion leading to parasite death,
- Disruption of parasite lifecycle in which these secondary metabolites interfered with the parasite's metabolic processes and development at various stages,
- Red blood cell (RBC) invasion where some flavonoid compounds can prevent the parasite from entering new red blood cells,
- Synergy with Artemisinin by which flavonoids particularly quercetin increased the efficacy of artemisinin suggesting potential for new combination therapies,
- Modulation of host pathways where flavonoids can influence host immune responses and cell signaling pathways involved in inflammation, further combating the disease malaria.

Saponins was multi-faceted and primarily involved the disruption of the parasite's host cell invasion process and the inhibition of key parasite proteins. Their

antiplasmodial effect was attributed to their amphipathic properties having both hydrophobic and hydrophilic parts which allowed them to interact with biological membranes and other cellular components. They have the ability to inhibit the growth of the malaria parasite *Plasmodium falciparum* with research indicating the work through multiple mechanisms including disrupting the parasite's membrane and targeting key proteins. Their special or key mechanisms included.

- Membrane disruption and cholesterol binding in which these compounds with cholesterol in cell membranes, including those of the parasite and the host red blood cells it invaded. This interaction perturbed and disorganized the cholesterol-rich lipid rafts, which were vital for the parasite's entry into cells and metabolism, thereby limiting host cell invasion,

- Protein invasion where saponin compounds can bind to specific parasite proteins. For example glycyrrhizin (GLR), a triterpenoid saponin from licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) bound to *Plasmodium falciparum* high-mobility group Box 1 (PfHMGB1) protein potentially inhibiting the parasite's transcriptional activity and growth.

- Enzyme inhibition in which some saponin metabolites like glycyrrhetic acid (GA) can inhibit the parasite's glyoxalase-1 (GLO-1) enzyme, a detoxification system essential for parasite survival.

Steroids acted as antiplasmodial agents by various mechanisms depending on the specific compound, but primarily involved disrupting the *Plasmodium* parasite-infected red blood cell (pRBC) membrane function, particularly the new permeability pathways (NPPs) the parasite created for nutrient uptake. Other mechanisms proposed included interference with hemoglobin digestion and induction of apoptotic-like cell death. They possessed significant antiplasmodial (anti-malarial) activity with various natural and synthetic steroid derivatives showing effectiveness against *P. falciparum*, the parasite causing malaria by disrupting its growth, affecting its metabolic pathways like hemozoin formation or ion transport, and even inducing parasite cell death through apoptosis-like mechanisms, leading to promising new drug candidates, particularly those with peroxide or specific side-chain modifications. Their key mechanism of action included.

- Inhibition of new permeability pathways (NPPS) demonstrated by some steroids such as those isolated from *Solanum nudum* (like SN2 and SN4) primarily acted on the infected red blood cell membrane by blocking the NPPS that the parasite created to acquire nutrients and dispose of waste. By inhibiting these pathways, the steroids interfered with the parasite's development and survival leading to its death.

- Interference with hemoglobin digestion where some steroids like Arymethylamino steroids, e.g. compound 1o, were thought to interfere with the parasite's hemoglobin (Hb) digestion pathway, a crucial process for the parasite's survival and growth. The steroid moiety might facilitate rapid internalization into the parasite's

food vacuole, where the active part of the molecule was bioactivated possibly involving metal or metal chelation to exert its toxic effect. This prevented the accumulation of toxic heme and preserved the food vacuole's integrity.

- Induction of apoptotic-like cell death caused by certain steroids as those from *S. nudum* which can induce characteristics of programmed cell death by apoptosis and autophagy and the parasite, like as a decrease in mitochondrial membrane potential, DNA fragmentation, and cytoplasmic acidification,

- Disruption of membrane function and merozoite invasion due to their lipophilic nature. Many steroidal compounds can incorporate into cell membranes, altering membrane properties like permeability and rigidity. This can inhibit the ability of new merozoites (the invasive stage) to invade uninfected red blood cells,

- Targeting parasite-specific proteins provoked by some hybrid steroid compounds like novel steroid-tetraoxane hybrids were being investigated for their ability to target specific parasite proteins such as *P. falciparum* Sarco/endoplasmic reticulum calcium-dependent ATPase (PfATP6) or cyclophilin, a protein linked to drug resistance. In summary, steroid compounds acted as antiplasmodial agents through multifaceted mechanisms, primarily by disrupting essential parasite processes, modifying host cell membranes and in some cases including cell death pathways as the specific mechanism was highly dependent on the compound's structure.

Terpenoids acted as antiplasmodial compounds through multiple often interconnected mechanisms, primarily by disrupting essential metabolic and cellular functions in the *Plasmodium* parasite. They possessed significant antiplasmodial or anti-malarial activity acting on the *Plasmodium* parasite by disrupting nutrient intake, inhibiting heme detoxification and targeting various stages of its lifecycle, with diverse structures such as diterpenoids and triterpenoids showing promise, exemplified by artemisinin, highlighting their potential as new leads especially against resistant strains. Their key mechanisms of action included.

- Heme-mediated activation as artemisinin was a widely used sesquiterpene lactone antiplasmodial or antimalarial drug, and its derivatives are activated by heme (iron) within the *Plasmodium* parasite's digestive vacuole. This effect generated carbon-centered reactive oxidants that bound to and inactivated crucial parasite proteins ultimately killing the parasite,

- Inhibition of phospholipid synthesis caused by some terpenoids such as those found in *Gardneria lucidum* plant extracts and appeared to inhibit the synthesis of phospholipids in infected erythrocytes. This was a crucial process for the rapidly growing parasite which required high amount of membrane material to survive and multiply,

- Disruption of cell membrane integrity was due to their lipophilic (fat-loving) nature. Many terpenoids can penetrate the parasite's cell membrane and disrupted its

structure and integrity. This led to metabolic instability, the loss of essential intracellular components like proteins, ions and even cell death,

-Interference with protein prenylation induced by certain terpenoid compounds like farnesol and nerolidol having been shown to inhibit the post-translational modification (isoprenylation) of cell-growth-regulating proteins like Ras and Rap in *Plasmodium* parasites. This disruption hindered the parasite's development, particularly in the schizont switched the parasite's stage,

- Inhibition of key metabolic enzymes as terpenoids can interfere with the parasite's isoprenoid biosynthesis pathway by inhibiting enzymes like isopentenyl diphosphate synthases or DXR (1-deoxy-D-xylose-5-phosphate reductoisomerase). Thus, equilibrium leading to the accumulation of reactive oxygen species that the parasite's endogenous systems, cannot manage causing oxidative damages an cell death.

- Interaction with and inhibition of parasite proteins: computational studies of some experimental evidence suggested that certain terpenoids like cucurbitacin B and β -O-acetyl oleanolic acid can bind to and inhibit essential *P. falciparum* proteins like plasmepsin II, histo-aspartic protein an falcipain-2.

In general, the observed antiplasmodial activity of extracts and solvent fractions from *T. gillettii* root bark could be attributed to the presence of secondary metabolites identified in this plant part because these different phytochemical such as alkaloids (Cimanga *et al.*, 2019, Soto-Vasquez *et al.*, 2021, Garcia-Duaz, 2025, Okom *et al.*, 2025), flavonoids (Chepkruai *et al.*, 2021, Abubakar *et al.*, 2020, Karania *et al.*, 2020, Ranaivoarison *et al.*, 2020, Tchangoue *et al.*, 2023), saponins (Akanbi *et al.*, 2018, Mafin *et al.*, 2021, Soecero *et al.*, 2021), steroids (Induani *et al.*, 2020, Safar *et al.*, 2022, Ngnoung *et al.*, 2020, Mianda *et al.*, 2020, Ranaivoarison *et al.*, 2020, Tchangoue *et al.*, 2023 Springer *et al.*, 2025), saponins (Akanbi *et al.*, 2018, Mafin *et al.*, 2021, Soecero *et al.*, 2021) and terpenoids (Helosa *et al.*, 2017, Greve *et al.*, 2020, Olayemi *et al.*, 2020, Ekasari *et al.*, 2023, Mabaza *et al.*, 2025) were previously reported to be endowed with this biological activity expressed with different magnitudes. Particularly, alkaloids can be considered as the one

active principle antiplasmodial of *T. gillettii* root bark since the crude alkaloids extract showed strong antiplasmodial effect in previous studies (Kikueta *et al.*, 2013) as confirmed in the present investigation.

The phytochemical analysis of aqueous AE and methanol ME extracts of *T. gillettii* root bark revealed the presence of different phytochemical constituents with alkaloids and flavonoids as predominant in both extracts. Alkaloids acted as antimalarial agents by inhibiting the production of protein and halting the conversion of toxic haem which resulted from the destruction of haemoglobin from being converted into haemozoin, a non-toxic pigment as previously reported by Herraiz *et al.*, 2019 and Evbuomwan *et al.*, 2025. Flavonoids had been reported to inhibit the transportation of myoinositol and L-glutamine into *Plasmodium*-myoinositol and L-glutamine played significant roles of the cycle of the parasite as also reported previously by Hamilton *et al.*, 2017 and Evbuomwan *et al.*, 2025. Based on this observation, it was suspected that total alkaloids from *T. gillettii* root bark may also react in the same way to exhibit its antimalarial effect *in vitro* test. Collectively, the antimalarial of the studied plant part in the present investigating may be attributed to its phytoconstituents acting probably in synergistic manner to exert strong antiplasmodial activity *in vitro* and *in vivo* and particularly in human treated with malaria in traditional medicine.

3.4. Observations in acute and subacute toxicity

After 28 days of observation in acute and subacute toxicity evaluation, no sign of toxic effects such as significant alteration in body weight, physical signs, symptoms, hematological, biochemical parameters, and body organ weights, hyperurination, abdominal muscle twitches, convulsions, salivation, aggression, rising furs, writhing and general behavior were not observed compared to the normal group. The liver, kidney, and stomach histology did not show any drug-induced lesion as also reported previously by Alelign *et al.*, (2020), Jawhari *et al.* (2021), Ur Rehman *et al.*, (2022). But mice in treated group with aqueous extract in acute at subacute toxicity gained body weight compared to negative control as illustrated in Figure 1 and 2 below.

Figure 2: Variation of bodyweight of mice in negative control and treated group in acute toxicity.

Figure 3: Variation of bodyweight of mice in negative control and treated group in subacute toxicity.

It was also observed that mice in subacute toxicity administered daily orally aqueous at oral dose of 5000 mg/kg bw showed high bodyweight than mice treated once with the same dose in acute toxicity as seen in figure 1 compared to figure 2. This difference must be due to the fact that the AE-1 extract at this high dose has a positive impact on appetite and food intake. No mortality of treated mice in both toxicity tests was observed and the lethal dose 50 (LD₅₀) was estimated to be greater than 5000 mg/kg bw. According to Suwandi *et al.*, (2021) and Jegnie *et al.* (2023), this extract can be considered as practically non-toxic by this administered way. According to toxicity classification, substances with lethal dose 50 (LD₅₀) values within the range of 1 to 5 g/kg bodyweight were generally considered to have low toxicity, while those having higher values than 5.0 g/kg bodyweight were generally considered to be non-toxic (Piyachaturavat *et al.*, 2002). Thus, as the LD₅₀ of aqueous extract from *T. gillettii* did not induce mortality of treated mice after 28 days of observation and its LD₅₀ consequently estimated to be greater than 5000 mg/kg bodyweight, it can be considered practically non-toxic per os route. Thus the *Trichlisia gillettii* root bark emerged safe to be used in the medicinal field for its pharmacological activity. Normally, this statement indicated that in a toxicity test involving mice, administering a high dosage of 5000 milligrams of a specific plant extract per kilogram of body weight did not result in any deaths among the treated animals. This suggests a low level of acute toxicity for that particular extract in mice at that dosage.

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